

EXPLORING MODULAR DISTANCE LEARNING EXPERIENCES OF GRADE 10 LEARNERS: BASIS FOR AN ACTION PLAN DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

One of the sectors greatly affected by the coronavirus pandemic is education. To make sure that learning remains unhampered as the country battles the pandemic, the Department of Education (DepEd) implemented the Modular Distance Learning Approach as an urgent response to ensure the continuity of education. The study was conducted to assess the learning experiences of Grade 10 learners in the implementation of the modular distance learning at Taal National High School. Assessing the experiences of the learners will be of great help for the school to design an action plan to address the needs of the learners. The research method that was utilized in the study is the descriptive method and research method utilizing the questionnaire as the main data gathering instrument containing different indicators based on their impressions for the last two grading periods. The study determined that learners' access to modular distance learning is very evident which signifies that learner can easily get the modules and learning activity sheets to each designated pick-up points, communicate with their teachers in various platforms like text messaging and Facebook. The data also revealed the importance of the weekly home learning plan in answering and completing the tasks on time. Teachers' assistance on providing corrections and clarifications on what is written on the module when needed is also very evident. Furthermore, majority of the learners has a problem encountered on the availability of study area at home due to lack of space. It was concluded that majority of the learners has a positive perception towards their modular distance learning experiences.

Keywords: Modular Distance Learning, Experiences, Descriptive Method, Taal National High School, Philippines